

Effects of Cement Dust Emitted by Dangote Cement Factory on Some Chemical Properties of Soils of Tse-Kucha, Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Some chemical properties of soils were assessed to determine the effects of cement dust emitted by the Dangote Cement Factory on the soils of Tse-kucha community within which the factory is situated. A soil profile pit was dug at Tse-kucha and soil samples were collected from each horizon of the profile pit for laboratory analysis. For comparison, samples were also collected from another profile pit dug at Gaando, a nearby community to Tse-kucha where there are no cement dusts in soils. The samples were analyzed for their chemical properties. Laboratory determinations made include; pH, organic carbon, exchangeable bases; Ca, Mg, Na and K, exchangeable acidity, available phosphorous, total nitrogen, CEC and percentage base saturation. The results obtained from the laboratory analysis of soils from the two study sites were then compared. The result showed that, pH and organic carbon content were significantly higher in soils of the affected areas than those of the unaffected areas due to the continuous deposition of cement dusts on the surface and leaching into deeper horizons. Also exchangeable acidity available phosphorous were slightly higher in soils of the affected areas, the result also showed that, exchangeable potassium, magnesium, total exchangeable bases, and cation exchange capacity were slightly higher in the unaffected soils but there was no significant difference in terms of total nitrogen, exchangeable cation and sodium, and percentage base saturation. Generally, the research showed that there was no significant difference in chemical properties between soils of the two study sites. Thus presently, the cement dust from the factory do not significantly affect the chemical properties of soils of the study area within which the factory is situated as the dust deposits only led to a slight but insignificant change in a few chemical properties but the variation is not significantly enough to cause a serious adverse effect on crop production.

Key words: chemical, cement dust, emitted, profile, soil properties, Tse-Kucha

Introduction

The establishment of any industry is basically and essentially to create wealth for the purpose of development and the provision of social and economic amenities. All these are aimed at the well-being and advancement of mankind. It is in such regard that the Dangote Cement Company was established in Tse-Kucha, Gboko local government area of Benue state. The establishment of

the industry as laudable as it may be has created problems to the area within which it is located (Tse–Kucha, Tse–Amua and Yandev) as a result of cement dust emission. It is on this basis that the research was set up. The research intends to identify the effects of the emitted cement dust from the company on the soils of the community within which it is located and possibly recommend ways of correcting such problems or effects so that the soils can become more useful for agricultural purposes and also seek ways to put a lasting end to the problems.

Cement is a powdery substance made by heating lime and clay, used to make mortar and concrete. The major raw material for cement production is limestone. Cement dust/cement kiln dust is a by-product of Portland cement manufacturing process. It is generated from burning the raw materials in a rotary kiln to produce clinker (Yahya, 2012). Cement factories are factories that are specialized in the manufacture, packaging and marketing of cement. Cement factories were established in Nigeria in response to the increased wave of construction after independence and during the oil boom era of the seventies (Oyedele *et al.*, 1990). It has been shown that cement factories constitute one of the worst polluters in Nigeria today (Akeredolu *et al.*, 1994). Establishment of these plants pre-dates strict industrial zoning regulations and hence their proximity to residential areas is now an issue of concern.

The soil is a thin layer of material on the earth's surface in which plants have their roots. It is made up of many things such as weathered rocks and decayed plant and animal matter. Soil is formed over a long period of time. Soil forms an integral part of the environment. The environment refers to the physical and biological components of the earth along with their chemical interactions that affects an organism. These components also include the soil which is the major study tool in this research.

Industries and factories whether private or government owned engage in production activities for the purpose of making profit. This sometimes endangers human health and the environment which includes the soil that is of great emphasis in this research.

Government in recent times beginning from the federal down to the local government level have been adopting ways of minimizing the effects of industrial pollution. Also, the federal and state governments set up bodies and programmes and annually recruit men into the bodies and programmes to reduce the effects of industrial pollution in the society. More worrisome is the seemingly unrealistic nature and inefficiency of these organizations in the reduction of industrial pollution in spite of huge government expenditure on environmental maintenance like the Benue State Environmental Sanitation Authority (BENSESA) among others and one would observe that, as more strategies are devised by the government to tackle the issue of industrial pollution, so too are the persistent increase of industrial pollution as a result of the increased number of industries in the society. The media on daily basis broadens our knowledge on the increasing cases of industrial pollution within Tse–Kucha community in Gboko area of Benue state within which the Dangote Cement Company is situated. The Dangote Cement Company, whose establishment in Gboko area has created a lot of problems to the host communities (Tse–Kucha, Tse–Amua and Yandev) between 1981 when it was established as Benue Cement Company till date (2014) as a lot of cement dust has been emitted into the environment thereby affecting the socio-economic activities of the host communities. Based on the above, the study is set to assess the effects of the emission of the cement dust from the Dangote Cement Factory on the soils of the host community (Tse–Kucha) and to proffer possible solutions to curb the problems.

Every manufacturing industry that uses raw materials has by-products which may be waste products that can be in solid, liquid or gaseous form. As wastes, they are generally disposed into the

environment of air, water or land where they may constitute serious hazard but when adequate precautions are taken, these wastes will not be hazardous. This study was embarked upon to assess the effects of cement dust emitted by the Dangote cement factory on some chemical properties of soils of Tse-Kucha community in Gboko area of Benue State.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Tse-Kucha is a community in Gboko local government area of Benue state. Tse-kucha lies within latitude $7^{\circ} 25' 26.4''$ N and longitude $8^{\circ} 58' 8.4''$ E. The elevation of Tse-Kucha is about 150 m above sea level. Generally, the area has a tropical climate. The climate here is classified as Aw (tropical rainy) by the Koppen-Geiger system. The average annual temperature in Tse-Kucha and Gboko as a whole is 26.8°C . It has a mean annual rainfall of about 1412 mm. The driest month is January with 3 mm. Most precipitation takes place in September with an average of 264 mm. The warmest month of the year is March with an average temperature of 29.4°C . In July, the average temperature is 25.4°C . It is the lowest average temperature of the whole year (NIMET, 2014).

The soils in Tse-Kucha are mainly sandy soils with clay sub-soils and the soils have a characteristic reddish colour. The soils are mainly Ultisols (tropical ferruginous) which vary over space with respect to texture, drainage and gravel content. A typical soil profile in Tse-Kucha is highly weathered with a sandy surface layer overlying a clay mottled sub-soil.

The vegetation of Tse-Kucha is that of the southern guinea savannah and the major type of land use is agriculture, building and few constructions. The occupation of the people of Tse-Kucha is mainly small-scale farming and petty trading.

Figure 1. Map of Benue State showing the study area.

Sample collection

Soil samples were collected from soil profile pits dug around the factory at a range of 0.8 km south of the factory. Basic method of soil profile research was used, one at the affected area (Tse-Kucha) where there has been cement dust deposition on soils for years and the other at Gaando where there are no cement dust deposits on soils to serve as the control area. Soil profiles were

described according to FAO (2006) guidelines while the soils were classified in line with USDA (2010) Soil Taxonomy. The various genetic horizons were then sampled for laboratory analysis. The samples were air-dried, crushed and passed through a 2 mm sieve for laboratory analysis.

Laboratory analyses

Standard procedures were employed in laboratory analysis. Laboratory determinations made include the following: pH (1:2.5 suspension in water), organic carbon (Walkley and Black, 1934 method), Exchangeable bases: Ca, Mg, Na, and K (extracted with 1N ammonium acetate at pH 7.0), exchangeable acidity (extracted with 1N KCl), available phosphorus (bray 1 method), total nitrogen was determined using the Kjeldahl procedure (Bremner, 1965) and the ECEC was calculated using the summation method.

Statistical analysis

T-test was the statistical technique used to test the significance of the difference in soil quality between the two study sites.

Results and Discussions

The chemical properties of soils as indicted in Table 1 shows the affected area (Tse–Kucha community) where there has been cement dust deposition for years, and unaffected area (Gaando Community) where there is no cement dust deposition on soils.

The pH of soils of the affected area had values ranging from 5.8 to 7.7 and was moderately acid to slightly alkaline when compared with the ratings of Chude *et al.* (2011). This is due to the deposition of cement dust on the soil. The soils pH of the unaffected area was strongly acid to slightly acid with values ranging from 5.5 to 6.0. The higher pH values in soils of the affected area were due to the deposition of cement dust on the soil because cement dust contains lime which is known to increase soil pH. The T-test results as presented in table 2 showed that the difference in pH between the two study sites was highly significant with a p-value of 0.001. Organic carbon content was slightly higher in soils of the affected area than those of the unaffected area having values between 0.04 to 0.80 and 0.98 to 1.36 respectively. According to Igomu and Idoga, (2017) the low organic carbon content of these soil units could be attributed to annual bush burning in the area as well as the native vegetation cover and climate. Drainage appeared to have strong influence on the organic carbon content of the soil. This can also be attributed to the accumulation and subsequent deposition of plant residues on the soil surface which are a source of carbon to the soil.

There is only a slight variation in available phosphorus between the two study areas. It is just slightly higher in the affected area than in the unaffected area. One of the factors that influences the availability of the element is soil pH (Brady and Weil, 1999; Landon, 1991). It becomes much more available at pH levels between 6.0 and 8.0 as found in the study area and becomes less available at lower pH levels (> 6.0) as found in the unaffected area, where the element is liable to be fixed by Al, Fe, and Mn (Euroconsult, 1985; Mizota and Van Reeuwijk, 1989). Since the pH of soils of the affected area lies mostly between 6.0 and 7.0, they contain more available phosphorus. There is no significant difference in the total nitrogen content between the two study sites and total nitrogen content was generally low in soils of both the affected and unaffected areas with values ranging from 0.05 to 0.06. Table 2 also shows that the difference in total nitrogen content between the two areas was insignificant with a p-value of 0.

Table 1. Chemical properties of the study areas (Tse-Kucha and Gaando Communities)

Horizon	Depth	pH (H ₂ O)	OC (%)	TN (%)	Av.P mg/kg	K	Na	Mg	Ca	EA	TEB	CEC (cmol/kg)	BS (%)
Soils of the affected area													
Ap	0-32	5.87	1.2	0.058	0.34	0.28	0.32	2.6	3.1	1.1	6.3	7.4	85.1
B	32-58	6.42	1.36	0.061	0.38	0.3	0.36	3.21	3.42	1	7.29	8.29	87.9
Bt1	58-86	6.6	1.04	0.056	0.32	0.27	0.31	3	3.2	1.01	6.78	7.79	87
Bt2	86-107	7.76	0.98	0.057	0.3	0.24	0.3	2.8	3.01	1.12	6.35	7.47	85
Soils of the unaffected area													
Ap	0-30	5.53	0.8	0.062	0.36	0.3	0.27	3	3.2	1.21	6.77	7.98	84.8
B	30-45	5.8	0.8	0.056	0.3	0.29	0.26	2.9	3	1.21	6.45	7.57	85.2
Bt1	45-110	5.97	0.38	0.06	0.38	0.34	0.32	3.2	3.42	1.1	7.28	8.38	86.9
Bt2	110-139	5.74	0.08	0.063	0.32	0.32	0.3	3.1	3.2	1	6.92	7.92	87.4
BC	139-169	6.06	0.04	0.064	0.34	0.32	0.31	3	3	1.1	6.64	7.74	85.8

OC= organic carbon, TN= total nitrogen, Av.P= available phosphorus, EA = exchangeable acidity, TEB = total exchangeable bases, BS = base saturation, CEC = cation exchange capacity

The values of exchangeable cations (Ca, Mg, K and Na) were low in all the soil units (Table 1). The low values of exchangeable bases of these soils maybe due to intensity of weathering and lateral translocation of bases Igomu and Idoga (2017). The amount of exchangeable calcium (Ca) ranged between 3.01 to 3.42 and 3.00 cmol/kg to 3.42 cmol/kg of soil, Magnesium (Mg) ranged between 2.60 to 3.21 and 2.90 to 3.20 cmol/kg of soil, Potassium (K) ranged between 0.24 to 0.30 and 0.29 to 0.32 cmol/kg of soil while Sodium (Na) ranged between 0.30 to 0.36 and 0.26 to 0.32 cmol/kg of soils of affected and unaffected areas respectively. The predominance of Ca over the other cations in these soils may be because of all the exchangeable cations, Ca is least easily lost from the soil environment Odoemena and Igomu (2017). Table 1 further shows that, Exchangeable Potassium (K) and Magnesium (Mg) were slightly higher in soils of the unaffected area (Gaando community) than those of the affected area (Tse-Kucha community) but the differences were insignificant with p-values of 0 and 0.01. Table 2 also shows that, there is no significant difference between the soils of the two study areas in terms of exchangeable Calcium (Ca) and Sodium (Na) content with p-values of zero (0) each. Exchangeable acidity was slightly higher in soils of the affected area than those of the unaffected area as shown in Table 1 but the difference was insignificant as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of statistical analysis

Soil variables	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
pH (H ₂ O)	6.66	9.99	5.82	10.41	158*	0.01
OC (%)	1.15	1.71	0.42	0.75	0.794*	0.01
TN (%)	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.11	0.154 ^{NS}	0
Av.P (mg/kg)	0.34	0.5	0.34	0.61	0.370 ^{NS}	0
K (coml/kg)	0.27	0.41	0.31	0.56	0.003 ^{NS}	0
Na (coml/kg)	0.32	0.48	0.3	0.52	0.043 ^{NS}	0
Mg (coml/kg)	2.9	4.36	3.04	5.44	0.129*	0.01
Ca (coml/kg)	3.18	4.78	3.17	5.66	0.089 ^{NS}	0
EA (coml/kg)	1.06	1.59	1.11	1.98	0.042 ^{NS}	0
TEB (coml/kg)	6.68	10.02	6.81	12.19	0.018 ^{NS}	0
CEC (coml/kg)	7.74	11.6	7.92	14.16	0.021 ^{NS}	0
BS (%)	86.25	129.38	86.02	153.88	2.435*	0.01

OC= organic carbon, TN= total nitrogen, Av.P= available phosphorus, EA = exchangeable acidity, TEB = total exchangeable bases, BS = base saturation, CEC = cation exchange capacity, SD= standard deviation

There was a slight difference in cation exchange capacity between the two study areas. It was just slightly higher in the unaffected soils. This could be due to the presence of more exchangeable cations and amount of clay in the soil. But Table 2 shows that there was no significant difference between the soils of the two study areas in terms of cation exchange capacity. Odoemena

and Igomu (2017) reported that some sandy soils of the tropics with dominant sesquioxide clay might have low CEC hence, low fertility.

The percentage base saturation was very high according to the ratings of Landon (1991), among the pedons. There is also no significant difference between the soils of the two study sites in terms of percentage base saturation and it ranges from 84.80 % to 87.90 % across the two study sites which is suitable for crop production.

Conclusions

Presently, the cement dust from the factory does not significantly affect the chemical properties of soils of the study area (Tse–Kucha Community) within which the factory is located as the dust deposits only led to a slight but insignificant change in a few chemical properties but the variation is not significant enough to adversely affect crop production. This agrees with the findings of Asadu and Agada, (2008).

Furthermore, the cement dust from the factory enhanced some of the selected chemical properties such as pH, exchangeable acidity and percentage base saturation and may manifest positively on crop performance around the area in the future. Hence if properly harnessed may contribute to soil fertility management in the affected areas. This is also in line with the research findings of Asadu and Agada, (2008) who also stated that the highest quantity of cement dust obtained in farm plots was only about 0.72t/ha/yr which is too small to cause any negative effects on soils and crops. This is because the company now has a way of collecting the dust within the factory instead of allowing it to spread out unlike in the past when the dust was being allowed to spread out.

Recommendations

Based on these research findings, the following management practices are recommended:

- ✓ Incorporation of crop residues to provide organic materials for the soil.
- ✓ Due to the low concentrations of Nitrogen in soils of the two study sites, farmers should adopt the use of high nitrogen fertilizers.
- ✓ There should also be installation of more dust collection equipment to further reduce dust emission during quarrying and manufacture of cement.
- ✓ There should also be an alternative use of dust trappings in air pollution control devices. It could be recycled for soil amendment for agricultural and other purposes.

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